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Urban Development in São Paulo and Hamburg.

Urban Materiality duality Catalogue for Slow mobility: Hamburg's Außenalster and São Paulo's Marginal Pinheiros.

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Introduction

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1. Introduction:

This project is a joint research between HCU HafenCity Universität Hamburg, Escola da Cidade São Paulo, Universidade de São Paulo and Leuphana Universität Lüneburg.

The project titled Urban Materiality duality Catalogue for Slow mobility: Hamburg's Außenalster and São Paulo's Marginal Pinheiros.

The project is supervised by the following Profs:

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- Thomas Hagedorn: (HafenCity Universität Hamburg)
- Ursula Kirschner: (Leuphana Universität Lüneburg)

The project takes place in Winter/Summer semesters for the academic year 2020/21.

The research was conducted by four group members:

1. **Felipe Silva**

From Quito, Ecuador. Currently doing his Bachelor studies in Urban and Regional Planning at the HCU Hamburg. Believes in the bicycle as the right tool for best transforming cities and prepare them for the future.

2. **Jan Straßburger**

From Hamburg, Germany, holds B.A. in Social Work from HAW Hamburg. Focuses are district work and citizen participation in urban planning. Worked as a trainee at the GWA St. Pauli (district work), the PlanBude (participation Paloma-Viertel St. Pauli) and TOLLER-ORT (office for participation in urban planning). Currently M.Sc. program Urban Design at the HCU Hamburg.

3. **Mariane Cardoso**

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From Alexandria, Egypt, holds B.Sc in Architecture from Alexandria University, Worked as Teaching assistant from 2019 at the same university, Currently M.Sc. of "Urban Planning and Policy design" at Politecnico di Milano, and doing Erasmus at Stadtplanung department at HCU HafenCity Universität Hamburg.

Methodology

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2. Methodology

a. Literature review

The basic concept of inspiration in the research is coming from Paola Viganò's concept of "*La città elementare*" The elementary city, which is perceiving the city as an independent element works altogether on the land itself, and these elements work together to create what is called the urban ecology.

The first attempt to define the urban ecology concept was in 1971, when Rayner Bahnam wrote his book "*Los Angeles: The Architecture of Four Ecologies*" and in his book, he turned his observation while driving a car in the city, how the different urban materials formed a four different urban ecologies in the city itself, he even give the city four names which demonstrates how the city preforms differentially based on the given materials: the flatlands (which Banham labeled the "Plains of Id"), the beach cities ("Surfurbia"), the freeways ("Autopia") and the foothills. (Banham 1971)

The urban materials are composition units of the urban space, which we can recognize in the specific relationship between built-up and open space. Perceiving the urban materials of a city is a way to sound/sample and interpret elements of the quality of its habitability.

But the question is, how would urban materiality be?

1. Fragmented / detailed:

Elementarism is not new in general, as it was used in the artistic approaches before, like in De Stijl work and Dadaism approach, the way that concept works is the elements to re-explore the new materials (Vigano 1999). It is aimed at reducing complexity and decodifying its forms, techniques, and means of expression. Assuming the condition of complexity of the city: the city as a place of difference and also repetition.

2. Deconstruction/Composition:

The re-compositional problem in the settled landscape occurs because of the modern industrial cities cycle ran out, in append, the upsurge demand on new vacancies in the metropolitan cities. That brings an unexpected place to be immersed again into the contemporary urban scenarios.

Rem Koolhaas presented the idea of Generic city, and Junk spaces, Koolhaas refers to giant "modern" architecture as an obstacle to the regeneration process. (Bonfantini 2018)

Architecture itself is a material, and the same would be applied to massive parking

Image no. 1: De Stijl, MoMA Bulletin Vol. XX No. 2, Winter 1952-3 Chronology and introductory essay by Alfred H. Barr, Jr.; foreword by Philip C. Johnson

Image no. 2: City Elements. Caravaggi

lots, underused vacant spaces, sieged or fenced parks. The bigger material could be, the harder it is re-composed in the urban space.

3. Simple to Complex Materials:

Observes the materials that make up the city, but also the way these materials articulate, generating complex systems.

b. Methodology

The research studies the city of Hamburg and Sao Paulo in parallel, as the main aim behind the research, is to figure out to which extend urban materiality is exchangeable between the two different cities, giving the slow mobility the intensive without excluding the relative materials.

The process of collecting the data was not linear, as in the beginning, definitions of urban materiality are being settled, work scope is well-defined as well. To narrow down the research focus, and to make the comparison more vivid, the two urban ecologies were set to meet a specific requirement to make the comparison as relevant as possible.

Ecologies must be close to the city centre, and to be integrated with the soft landscape (blue or green), also the presence of leisure or sport bike lanes would be important to see how such mobility system could integrate with the built-up nature, therefore, and according to the mentioned criteria, Hamburg's Außenalster and São Paulo's Marginal Pinheiros were selected to be made as study prototype. The materials were collected onsite in the case of Hamburg, and in Sao Paulo google street view was used to investigate the environment, afterwards, materials were cropped and collected in Miro platform, where they got collected and categorized. Then, data was investigated and put into a comparison with the other city, finally, a photo collage is being made from the catalogue materials which supposed to show to which extend transferring urban materials is possible.

Image no. 3: Materials clusters as per ecology at [Miro platform](#), researchers

*Background
analysis*

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3. Background analysis:

a. Hamburg

The city of Hamburg with a population of approximately 1.85 million is the 2nd largest city in Germany and the 7th largest city in the European Union (Statistikamt Nord 2020). The metropolitan area of the city is home to more than five million people. Hamburg is famous for its port which is the largest seaport in Germany and one of the most important hubs in the world economy. The development of the city has been linked to the port for centuries as the port being the economic engine of the city. The history as a port city also brought a lot of international cultural influence to the city which creates a heterogeneous metropolis. The metropolitan area of Hamburg is one of the strongest economic regions in Germany.

Like other cities in Germany after WW2, Hamburg got rebuilt in the 1950s with the paradigm of the car-friendly-city (Bardua and Kähler 2012:22 ff.). In the late 70s, the agenda of many German cities changed and investments into bicycle infrastructure were rising. Especially smaller student cities distinguished within that development (Meyer 2016:85 f.) Hamburg, which was (is still) relying on the port as the main economic force was much slower with these priority changes and created further needs for motorized transport infrastructure in the 1970s - like the city highway "Hafenquerspange".

Nevertheless, since the 2010s the government in Hamburg admitted more importance to the bicycle as a mode of transport and the spendings for bicycle infrastructure were constantly rising. In 2011 the city spent approximately 5.5 million Euros on bicycle infrastructure and cycling promotion, while in 2017 the spendings were raised to approximately 19.5 million Euros (Hamburgische Bürgerschaft 2018). This equals 10,56 Euro per inhabitant (in 2017) which is a significant increase over the last years but still quite little compared to "real" bicycle friendly cities like Copenhagen. In comparison, Copenhagen spends an average of 35,60 Euro per inhabitant on bicycle infrastructure every year (City of Copenhagen 2017).

Project: Alster fahrradachsen

History & Official Protagonists:

The project "Alster Fahrradachsen" was initiated in 2013 in the context of the "Fahrradwerkstatt" workshop, a meeting of the district chiefs with the first mayor to improve the bicycle infrastructure over the districts. Because the district of the Außenalster lies within three governmental districts a masterplan for the whole project was commissioned to Argus PartGmbH (urban and traffic planning) and the steg Hamburg GmbH (city renewal and development corporation). The project is financed by the City of Hamburg.

Goals & Benefits:

The project's goal is to develop the much used bicycle lanes around the Alster to make them suitable for actual and future requirements. Safe, quick and comfortable cycling should be granted due to modern bicycle roads and lanes (Behörde für Wirtschaft und Innovation n.d.).

Additionally the Außenalster is a very popular and representative place for the City of Hamburg and a hotspot for tourists and free time activities. Therefore the project aims for an improvement of the

green spaces and the urban design of the public space (Behörde für Wirtschaft und Innovation n.d.).

Image no. 4: Visualisation of a contemporary bicycle road at the Außenalster, argus-hh.de

Planning and Methods

The Alster is a central barrier for the traffic in Hamburg which leads to Hamburg's highest emergence of bicycle traffic along the waterfront. Complex surveys, observations, interviews with cyclists and a traffic flow analysis were made which were showing the need for comprehensive improvements for the bicycle infrastructure (ARGUS Stadt und Verkehr n.d.). For example, a deficit analysis showed that approximately 60% of the routes around the Außenalster have a higher rise of bicycle traffic than car traffic and therefore the construction of full bicycle roads at these routes was suggested (Behörde für Wirtschaft und Innovation n.d.). After the analysis five different sections were identified and special concepts and proposed measures were created for each of them. The realization of the proj-

Image no. 5: Functioning of the Alster Fahrradachsen for cycling mobility, LSBG Hamburg

Image no. 6: Construction Sections Alster Fahrradachsen , LSBG Hamburg
 Project started with the completion of a pilot route in December 2014.

Realization

The pilot route was completed in December 2014. The construction of the first section started in September 2017 and should be finished in summer 2021. In summer 2018, the realization of the second section (which got divided in two subsections) was started. It is planned to finish the construction of the second section in autumn 2021.

b. Sao Paulo

São Paulo is a metropolis located in Brazil ([Image no.7](#)), and consists of a city that represents the main financial, corporate and commercial center in South America (Pimenta, 2007). Located in the homonymous state ([Image No. 8](#)), the municipality has around 12 million inhabitants, in addition to another 9 million who are inserted in the metropolitan region, totaling more than 21 million people who live in its territory (IBGE, 2020). It is, according to 2018 United Nations estimates, the fourteenth largest city on the globe (Prado, 2020).

[Image no. 7](#):Brazil, *Googlemaps*

In this way, it is configured as a very heterogeneous metropolis, which brings together different spaces and materialities in its territorialities. The size and heterogeneity of the city are present not only in the size and diversity of its economy, but also in the differences observed in its internal regions, whose rhythms of population growth, age profiles and unemployment rates are different in each neighborhood. Thus, one of the major problems of the city is social inequality, as it is a municipality in which “[...] millions of people are separated by access (or lack thereof) to fundamental public goods and services” (Nossa São Paulo, 2020). The challenges, therefore, are multiple, requiring public authorities to focus on addressing the problems arising from these characteristics.

[Image no. 8](#):Sao Paulo, *Googlemaps*

The Master Plan approaches this issue by integrating and articulating different means of transportation. It stipulates minimum and permanent investments for improving the public transportation system, as well as the infrastructure for non-motorized means of transportation (bicycles and pedestrians), which are less polluting. (City of Sao Paulo, 2014, p.8)

Within this context, we chose Marginal Pinheiros ([Image no.9](#)) as a research space for slow mobility in the city.

[Image no. 9](#):Marginal Pinheiros, *Googlemaps*

Marginal Pinheiros

The Marginal Pinheiros is the second most important expressway in the city of São Paulo. It borders the Pinheiros River, an important hydrographic course that makes up the city's landscape. In this set of avenues, one of the most important points is the University City of the University of São Paulo, but there are also commercial zones, mixed zones, sports spaces, parks, in addition to the presence of Ceagesp, an important reference in urban supply, being the third largest retail food center in the world. That said, it is important to note that this set of avenues has undergone major transformations in recent decades, expanding its urbanization process and receiving the construction of several skyscrapers.

The Marginal Pinheiros Cycle Path is the longest bike path in the Metropolitan Region of São Paulo. Inaugurated on February 27, 2010, by CPTM - São Paulo Metropolitan Trains Company - the complete bike path (Figure 4) is 21.5 kilometers long (CPTM, 2021). We take the path that goes from Parque do Povo, or People's Park, to Parque Villa-Lobos, or Villa-Lobos Park (Image No. 10), a path that comprises about 8km.

Its opening hours are currently limited, from 5:30 am to 6:30 pm. The path is isolated between the banks of the Pinheiros River, on one side, and the CPTM public transport train line, on the other. This means that, during most of the journey that the cyclist travels, the materialities to which he has contact strongly limit his reading of the city.

Image no. 10: Pinheiros Bike Path. Source: *Google Maps*.

The river, however, has serious problems regarding its water pollution. Currently, it is undergoing a clean-up process directed by the government of the State of São Paulo, whose goal is to clean up the river by 2022 (Ribeiro, 2021). The Novo Rio Pinheiros Program aims to clean up the watercourse through a major basic sanitation project, maintenance actions, in addition to the recovery of margins with the support of the private sector (State of São Paulo, 2020).

Image no. 11: People's Park to Villa-Lobos Park. *adapted from Google Maps*

In March 2020, the government handed over the bike path, located on the east bank of the river, to the private sector for an extendable period of three years. The company Farah Service “[...] which has been active in the revitalization of urban public areas for 33 years, [was responsible for] maintenance, signaling, cleaning and gardening of the 21.5 km of cycle lane” (CPTM, 2020, online). In the beginning of the year 2021, some sections of the bike path have already been modified, with the installation of bathroom and locker room services, totems to charge cell phones, cafes, machines to sell snacks (Image No 12 and 13).

In 2021, the government of São Paulo announced a call for companies interested in building a park on the west bank of Rio, establishing the Parque Novo Rio Pinheiros Consortium. This consortium consists of the companies Amarilis - representative of the Global Park - Farah Service, Jardiplan and Metalu Brasil (São Paulo, 2021, online). Along with the CPTM Bike Path and the Usina SP concession,

Image no. 12: Bike Path. Source: *Farah Service/Instagram, 2021*

Image no. 13: Modified Bike Path. Source: *Secretaria dos Transportes Metropolitanos, 2021*

this is the third action of the current government under the revitalization axis with private investment.

Catalogue

Blue and green materials.

0 100 200 300 400 500 600 m

0 100 200 300 400 500 600 m

Material index:

B&G.SP_1

Material Name:

Green topography

A green topography made to separate cycle lanes from other functions using grass and some slim tree lines.

Material Description:

Despite having an even surface might seem not acceptable in public spaces, but, on the other hand that could be useful in order to mitigate with climate effects "floods", likewise in Copenhagen's Enghaveparken public, topology were made to be flooded, the adaptable-resilient approach gives the urban materiality more strength.

Relative Material:

Material index:

B&G.HH_1

Material Name:

Open public space

Material Description: Accessible open public space used for barbecuing and boat watching. This space is heavily used during the summer days because it offers a view of the city's skyline and enough space to gather with friends and family..

Relative Material: Having open public space in front of a body of water is a luxury only few cities in the world have. A prime example is the development carried along the waterfront in Vancouver, Canada, where lots of green open space has been created for the people and businesses to have direct access to the river, thus creating highly attractive public/ private spaces.

4. Mobility

Material index:

M.SP_001

Material Name:

Cobble stone street

Material Description: Brick road mainly for cars with a sidewalk for pedestrians made from the same material, no specific bicycle signs, meaning is a shared street. This street allows for a low-speed traffic for both motorized vehicles and bicycle users. The width of the street also contributes to this attribute, making it more appealing for other modes of transport to be used as well as the physical separation from the walkway to facilitate pedestrian movement.

Relative Material: As seen on the iconic streets of Paris, two designs made of cobble stones were implemented specifically to facilitate transport by bicycle. The cobble stones on the left are placed horizontally for cars to drive on, and the design on the right are placed vertically, so that the bicycle ride is as smooth as possible. This designs are used so that the iconic and historic appearance of cobble stone streets of Paris were not lost and to facilitate multimodal transport.

Material index:

M.HH_1

Material Name:

Dirt road for pedestrians and paved road for bicycles

Material Description: Dirt road for pedestrians while brick road for bicycles, no access to cars. This shared road circumnavigates the Alster lake which allows a higher flow of non-motorized traffic in comparison to the rest of the city streets. There is a clear demarcation of the pedestrian path and the bicycle path. Bicycles can ride on pavement which eases smooth transport. The bicycle path is a two-way path which should be enlarged due to high number of users.

Relative Material: In this example seen in the streets of Copenhagen, one can see very clearly how much space is given to bicycles and how much to pedestrians. The whole street is made up of the same material, thus expressing the priorities of the city regarding non-motorized traffic.

5. Built environment

0 100 200 300 400 500 600 m

100 0 100 200 300 400 500 600

Material index:

Env.SP_1

Material Name:

Garbage can

Material Description: Plastic, seamless, genral use garbage can with a little sign of recycling.

Relative Material: This is an example of how the design of garbage cans in Canada can help to sustain much more efficiently our cities. Instead of a single use trash can, were people throw away all kind of materials, they could be replaced by multiple-use trash cans were people separate their trash, thus contributing to a circular economy saving millions of currency per year.

Material index:

Env.HH_1

Material Name:

Garbage

Material Description: This sign used to indicate where the bicycle path follows, has multiple uses because it serves the purpose of a garbage can too.

As seen in the streets of Copenhagen, tilted garbage cans help people throw away their trash while on the go. This clever design made by Copenhagenize Design Co. has been replicated in many cities around the world because of its practicality, cool esthetics and user friendliness.

Material index:

Env.SP_2

Material Name:

High-rise Building

Material Description:

High rise building, multiple apartments, middle-class families. Building located along the Pinheiros river.

Relative Material:

High rise residential buildings are a great way to contribute to a mix and condense urban area. As seen in Hong Kong, one of the most densely populated cities in the world, the use of residential skyscrapers contribute to the relatively high lifestyle of its people. This is because high rise residential buildings do not take much space on the ground and house a much greater amount of people than that of its European counterparts. Sao Paulo could greatly benefit from such buildings because as one of the mega cities of the world, Sao Paulo takes up an incredible amount of space because it does not follow a dense and mixed way of developing the urban fabric. As seen on the picture above, Sao Paulo should replicate more of Hong Kong's urban development in order to sustain the inevitable urban and population growth.

Material index:

Env.HH_2

Material Name:

Villa

Multiple-story Villa House along the Alster lake in Hamburg. High-class, modern apartments with classical architecture.

Relative Material:

An example of high-class Villas in Italy. The amount of space that the whole compound takes up is much less sustainable than that of Hamburg. Villas that are located along the Alster lake do not have pools or large private gardens, that way complimenting the surrounding areas by not taking much space like seen on the picture below. High-class Villas are considered that way because of the Victorian architecture and because of the privileged location which only few can afford. Eventhough people with a lot of money live in these houses, they do not take up much space and mix very well with the urban fabric.

Material index:

Env.SP_3

Material Name:

Service building

Material Description: Water pump service building with a touch of urban art.

Material index:

Env.HH_3

Material Name:

Road sign + garbage

Material Description: Multiple service building along the Alster lake serves its purpose as a place for pedestrians and bicycle users stop and refresh their thirst.

Relative Material:

With arts and culture being such of importance to the livability of the city, authorities must support its artists and its creative community in order to promote cultural diversity and the arts. As seen in the picture below, a Vancouver kiosk has been turned into a work of art, as a product of the newly introduced a Creative City Plan in order to enhance the cultural development of the city, represented in ordinary buildings.

Relative Material:

The picture above is a service building that serves multiple purposes like a shop where people can buy snacks and beverages as well as fix their bikes. An example of a much smaller, and effective way to offer the exact same services, is seen at a service station of bicycles in the Netherlands. It is a simple, but effective way to service one self when in need of repairing a bicycle or buying something to eat or drink. Additionally, one could even buy tools directly from the vending machine for the use of bicycle repairs.

Material index:

Env.SP_4

Material Name:

Sticker Marielle

Material Description:

A sticker containing the face of Marielle Franco, Brazilian councilor and human rights defender, murdered in 2018 for political reasons.

This small sticker reveals a dimension of the social conflicts present in Brazil. Marielle, defender of human rights, black woman, lesbian, councilor in favor of the removal of militant posts from the favelas of Rio de Janeiro, became a symbol of resistance after being assassinated for political reasons. The crime, still unsolved today, reflects the links between government officials and the militia. Such material reveals that the Brazilian dilemmas go beyond the architectural resolutions of urban development.

Material index:

Env.HH_4

Material Name:

Art Stickers

Material Description:

Stickers posted door, the stickers could be founded on "almost" any vertical service in Außenalster and all over Hamburg, it could be tapped on signs, traffic light and bridge's rail, normally in a place where it could be seen. The stickers represents high range of statements, from personal to public, from football to politics, from dark to sarcasm.

*Conclusion/
Collage*

5

We analyzed the materiality of the two slow mobility spaces in Hamburg and Sao Paulo with the help of a wide range collection of materials. The materials were cropped and collected on a visual online platform (Miro) and sorted into categories. Paola Viganò's theoretical concept of the Elementary City helped us to understand the different perspectives on the collected urban materiality like fragmentation/detailing, deconstruction/composition and simple to complex materials. With this knowledge, we created the urban materiality duality catalogue where we showed selected urban materials from Hamburg and Sao Paulo in comparison and in relation to relative spaces in other cities. The final step was the creation of an urban collage, which is a new formation and visual conclusion of the material catalogue. The aim of the urban collage is to match different materialities out of our catalogue and material collection together to create a new urban fabric suitable for the demands of slow mobility. We combined materialities from different categories to create an extensive idea of a combined urban materiality. Different mobility materialities, like a colored bicycle road and pedestrian sidewalk, allow a safe and comfortable movement for slow mobility. Cars are blocked from the area by different barriers (bollards, railings), which means they cannot get in conflict or endanger other traffic users. The built environment consists of different service buildings, green space, trashcans and play equipment to fulfil the needs of the users of the space. The residential buildings are mixed, from high-rise buildings to villa houses to represent diversity and should be integrated into the public space instead of being (or feeling) separated.

Slow mobility material collage from the two cities composed together.

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